

Surprising widespread of the bayesvl package

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Data on RDocumentation (CRAN) shows that the bayesvl R package had an exceptionally high number of downloads in January 2024 compared to December 2023, with an increase of 164%. This excitement motivated me to investigate the extent of bayesvl's spread further, leading to the discovery of two interesting pieces of information.

Firstly, the statistics from datasciencemeta.com caught my attention. I am uncertain about the nature of this website or its creator. Still, I found it intriguing that the total download count for bayesvl was not 9,568 as reported on RDocumentation but more than double: 21,284. This figure ranks bayesvl at 11,324 out of 20,332 packages on CRAN: <https://www.datasciencemeta.com/rpackages>

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How to Use the bayesvl Package in R

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Learn how to install, load, and use the bayesvl package in R with our beginner's guide. We provide real examples and useful tips to help you master this essential tool.

Details

bayesvl is an R package that provides tools for visualizing Bayesian networks. It includes functions for specifying networks, conducting inference, and creating plots. This can help users understand the structure and implications of their Bayesian networks.

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A bayesvl usage guide on R Basics

In addition to the mentioned statistics, I found an independently created guide on using the bayesvl package. This guide is provided by R Basics, a community offering programming tutorials for those new to R: <https://rbasics.org/guides/how-to-use-the-bayesvl-package-in-r/>.

These signals suggest that the bayesvl package is spreading widely, surpassing my and the team's tracking capabilities. Perhaps the reason behind this widespread adoption lies in the use of the BMF analytics and mindsponge theory in research. Or is it due to the availability of previously published software guides?

It could be both reasons or even more. Regardless, this is undoubtedly good news for both myself and the bayesvl and BMF development team.

References

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